

The Minimum Cell – minimum housing standards: Minimum as Maximum

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Abstract: The present study aims to reflect on the house's minimum living space through its functional and spacial features, throughout architectural models of the so-called 'social housing', where budget restraints and the need to dignify the habitat coexist. Spacial and formal restrains are therefore defined as the main concerns in an architectural research, meaning that 'minimum' thinking does also apply to a daily architectural practice, where there's a need to balance the 'desired' house with the 'possible house'. Therefore, the importance of the present proposal is manifested in an evaluation of Architecture as a comprehensive practice, analyzed in its contemporary context and establishing parameters that will be applied in new housing proposals. The proposed paper therefore tries to define Architecture as a widespread benefit capable to define and apply criteria so it can accomplish its intentions. The main architectural movements will be mentioned through their practical and theoretical ideals who express the principles of spacial definition and its correlation with the individual and the surrounding environment. However, in this article, it will be made a special mention to the Neo-realism movement from the post-World War II period, where the admissible minimum was intended as the maximum possible.

Keywords: Neo-realism, Modernism, Housing.

Alexander Glass PROTOTYPE

LEGEND

Prototype

- Hall
- WC
- Corridor
- Stairs
- Chapel
- Living/Dining Room
- Kitchen
- Corridor
- Bedroom
- Bedroom

Scale 1:1000

Project

Location: Central project
 Address: Riverside Mall
 Date: 2008
 Architect: Central project

Association of the cell
 Access: Closed
 Type: 7.5 (three bedrooms)

Room/Category	Area (sqm)	Ratio (%)	Total
Type	60.7	75.2%	
Living Area	102.0		
Private Spaces	112.0	88.2%	125.0
Living/Dining Room	2.2	1.7%	11.0
Kitchen	10.0	7.9%	10.0
Bedroom	20.0	15.8%	37.4%
Total	20.0	15.8%	37.4%
Public Spaces	11.0	8.7%	11.0
Hall	1.2	0.9%	1.2
WC	1.0	0.8%	1.0
Bedroom	8.8	6.9%	8.8
Total	11.0	8.7%	11.0
Other Areas	11.0	8.7%	11.0
Hall	1.2	0.9%	1.2
WC	1.0	0.8%	1.0
Bedroom	8.8	6.9%	8.8
Total	11.0	8.7%	11.0
Total	8.4	6.6%	8.4
Total (Public Area)	12.4	9.8%	12.4

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